

SCIENCE IN THE REPUBLIC OF KARAKALPAKSTAN

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Abstract: *In this article examined about the issue of the day in historical science in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, devoted histories of development of the system of education. In the years of independence considerable changes assisting the economy and social growing happened in life of republic. Reforms in area of education gave the positive results. By the proclaimed priority sphere of development are all the constituents of enormous historical meaningfulness in life of people of region, a comprehension of that is the actual task of science of independent republic is analyzed.*

Key words: *Central Asia, Karakalpakstan, Nukus, city, identity, industrial cities, historical science, education, independence, development, system education, new approach, transformation, historical process.*

Topical issues of the historical science of Uzbekistan and Karakalpakstan include studies on the history of the development of the education system. The path traversed from the confessional education of the late XIX century to the new secular system on the principles of the European school after the conquest of Turkestan by the Russian Empire (the

emergence of primary schools, reading and writing, urban schools, Russian-native schools, women's parochial schools, new-fashioned Jadid schools); the struggle for the elimination of illiteracy in Uzbekistan and Karakalpakstan, the introduction of universal primary education, the implementation of the program of universal education, specialized

secondary and higher education in the Soviet period; creation of a new educational system in the period of independence of Uzbekistan.

The Republic of Uzbekistan and the Republic of Karakalpakstan have entered a qualitatively new period of their historical development and are on the way to creating truly democratic national states on a legal basis [1. P. 34-37]. This period is characterized by fundamental changes in their socio-political and public life. They were due to the following events and circumstances: On August 31, 1991, at the extraordinary sixth session of the Supreme Council of Uzbekistan, a declaration of state independence was adopted, on the basis of which the Law “On the basis of state independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan» [2. P. 9-11]. For the first time in history, the sovereignty of the Republic of Karakalpakstan was adopted in it, proclaiming it at the end of 1990. Thanks to the renewal, the transition began to a democratic social and state system, called upon to be the basis for subsequent development in the name of man.

Independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the sovereignty of the Republic of Karakalpakstan [6. P. 87] are protected by the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan [3. P. 98.]. In the life of the republic there have been significant changes that contributed to economic and social growth. Reforms in education have yielded positive results. The proclaimed priority area of development is all components of enormous historical significance in the life of the peoples of the region, the understanding of which is an urgent task of the science of an independent republic.

It is well known that without solving these most complicated tasks in the field of education, historical progress in society’s life, regional withdrawal from the state of economic and social stagnation, creation of the foundations of an industrial society’s infrastructure, including the first models of the most advanced forms of education, would not be possible. The search for an independent path of development after the collapse of the USSR led Uzbekistan to create its own

model of the education system necessary for the life and development of a sovereign state. During the years of independence, large-scale measures were implemented in the Republic of Karakalpakstan aimed at fulfilling the requirements of the Law on Education and the National Training Program, Decrees and Resolutions of the President and the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which support deepening of educational reforms. During the years of independence, government spending on the social sphere increased by more than 5 times, each year about 60 percent of the budget goes to the development of health care, education, public utilities, social protection of the population and other industries[4. P. 554.].

The uniqueness of the Uzbek model of training of personnel is recognized by the entire world community. The model of education of Uzbekistan includes not only physical objects, which themselves are first-class. The model of education is based on quality - the quality of teachers, students, programs and, ultimately, the quality of knowledge. The Uzbek

model of education takes into account the needs associated with globalization, and is a tool to ensure a positive and productive role of Uzbekistan in Asia and beyond.

Analysis of international experience shows that in many developed countries, reforms in this area were carried out, as a rule, only in the education system, were not as large in scope and depth of coverage, scientific validity, participation of the entire society in them, as is the case in Uzbekistan. The main distinctive feature of the National Program is its integrity, a systematic approach, where the individual, the state and society, continuing education, science and production are components of a single process.

Uzbekistan is the center of culture, art, science and education in Central Asia, the birthplace of many great thinkers, scientists and teachers, such as Alisher Navoi, Zahiriddin Muhammad Bobur, Mirzo Ulugbek, Ahmad al-Fergani, Abu Rayhan Beruni, Abu Ali Ibn Sina, classics of Karakalpak literature like Berdakh, Azhinyaz and many others. Their

intellectual heritage has influenced the upbringing and development of many generations of people, not only in this vast region, but also far beyond its borders - in Europe, Asia and the Middle East. Throughout its history, the Uzbek and Karakalpak people have maintained a deep commitment to the development of culture and science. So it is in modern Uzbekistan, where the national educational policy is based on this rich heritage. The history of education is full of events that have influenced development, both positively and negatively. The history is very controversial, but this is our history [5. P. 164.]. In the last quarter of the XX - early XXI century in the life of the peoples of Karakalpakstan, profound political, economic, social and cultural changes took place. The urgency of the problem is also due to the fact- the study of this problem according to the achievements of modern science is aimed at introducing into scientific circulation archival documents based on the concept of the history of the independence period of Uzbekistan and Karakalpakstan.

The practice of training qualified national personnel is of great scientific and practical importance not only for Karakalpakstan and Uzbekistan, but also for other republics that have embarked on the path of national revival. At the moment, many previously unexplored historical facts of the formation and development of the education system and the training of qualified national personnel in Karakalpakstan at the beginning of the 20th and 21st centuries are reflected in the research.

In line with this, reforms of the education system in the Republic of Karakalpakstan during the period of independence are being studied, stages of transformations in pre-school, secondary, secondary special education and higher education are considered in the context of economic and social development, environmental problems, restoration of spirituality and the study of national heritage;

- analyze the progress of implementation and additions of the new Laws “On Education” and “On the National Program for Personnel

Training” (1997) in the Republic of Karakalpakstan.

The materials of the secret unlearned funds of the Central State Archive of the Republic of Uzbekistan (CSARUz) are studied; Central State Archive of the Republic of Karakalpakstan (CSARKr); Materials of the current archives of Karakalpak State University by named of Berdah; The Ministry of Education of the Republic of Karakalpakstan; The Ministry of Culture and Sports of the Republic of Karakalpakstan; Council

of Ministers of the Republic of Karakalpakstan (department of science, culture and education).

Historical processes and new transformations in the education system of 2017–2021 require a conceptual rethinking of many issues of the history of Karakalpakstan of the last quarter of the 20th - beginning of the 21st centuries. and development of new approaches in the study of the history of the education system of the Republic of Karakalpakstan.

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